

Figure 2. SPPH etiologies **A.B.** in different midwifery hospitals. **C.D.** in patients without/with antenatal PPH risk factors. The SPPH etiologies are divided as four “T”. Tone – atonic uterus; Tissue – retained placental tissue and placenta accreta spectrum disorders; Trauma – soft birth canal injury, i.e. perineal laceration, hematoma of perineum and vaginal wall, cervical tears, rupture of uterus, inversion of uterus, and intraoperative vascular injury, etc. Thrombin – coagulation disorder dysfunction, can be divided into inherited, such as von Willebrand diseases, hemophilia, and acquired, such as the use of anticoagulant therapy and the occurrence of disseminated intravascular coagulopathy after placental abruption, pre-eclampsia with severe features, or amniotic fluid embolism.